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Inconsistencies in the EU regulatory risk assessment of PFAS call for readjustment

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ABSTRACT

Recognition of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) as widespread environmental pollutants and a consequent risk to human health, has recently made the European Union (EU) adopt several regulatory measures for their management. The coherence of these measures is challenged by the diversity and the ubiquitous occurrence of PFAS, which also complicates the EU's endeavor to advance justified, harmonized, and transparent approaches in the regulatory assessment of chemical risks. Our study critically reviews the European approach for the risk assessment of PFAS, by applying a comparative analysis of the current and pending regulatory thresholds issued for these chemicals in water bodies, drinking water, and certain foodstuffs. Our study shows that the level of health protection embedded in the studied thresholds may differ by three orders of magnitude, even in similar exposure settings. This is likely to confuse the common understanding of the toxicity and health risks of PFAS and undermine reasonable decision-making and the equal treatment of different stakeholders. We also indicate that currently, no consensus exists on the appropriate level of required health protection regarding PFAS and that the recently adopted tolerable intake value in the EU is too cautious. Based on our analysis, we propose some simple solutions on how the studied regulations and their implicit PFAS thresholds or their application could be improved. We further conclude that instead of setting EU-wide PFAS thresholds for all the environmental compartments, providing the member states with the flexibility to consider case-specific factors, such as regional background concentrations or food consumption rates, in their national regulatory procedures would likely result in more sustainable management of environmental PFAS without compromising the scientific foundation of risk assessment, the legitimacy of the EU policy framework and public health.

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a large group of synthetic chemicals that have been used in numerous industrial applications and consumer products since the early 1950s (Prevedouros et al., 2006). Alongside their extensive and long-term usage, many PFAS are very persistent having resulted in their ubiquitous presence in the environment covering all the biotic and abiotic matrices from remote locations to urban surroundings (Ahrens, 2011, Brusseau et al., 2020, Kurwadkar et al., 2022, Smalling et al., 2023). According to the most recent estimates, there are more than 12,000 partially or fully fluorinated compounds in the PFAS family, covering polymeric and non-polymeric substances with diverse chemical structures and properties (US EPA, 2021). Perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) including perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (PFCAs), such as perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), and

perfluoroalkyl sulfonic acids (PFSAs), such as perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), are essentially non-degradable and the most commonly detected and studied PFAS to date (ITRC, 2023). Polyfluoroalkyl substances, such as fluorotelomer sulfonates (FTSAs) and fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), on the other hand, may degrade to persistent PFAAs and are thus called their precursors (Buck et al., 2011).

In addition to their persistence, many PFAS are toxic, bio-accumulative, water-soluble, and mobile when released in the environment. Hence, they can adversely affect terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems or cause risks to human health, for example, via migration to drinking water or accumulation in food (Ghisi et al., 2019, Vestergren and Cousins, 2013, Noorlander et al., 2011). Based on current regulatory criteria and risk-based screening values, human exposure to PFAS at typical background concentrations (i.e., widespread contamination arising from diffuse sources) is generally a more critical issue than

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ecological exposure, at least for long-chain PFAAs (Ankley et al., 2021, ITRC, 2023, Ruffle et al., 2023). Exposure to PFAS has been associated with a variety of adverse health effects, including altered immune function, liver and kidney disease, lipid and insulin dysregulation, reproductive and developmental disorders, and cancer (Fenton et al., 2021). The main source of PFAS for human exposure in the general population is diet, which generally accounts for more than 70 % of the total intake in Europe (EFSA, 2020). The food items causing the majority of PFAS exposure vary between different PFAS, geographical regions, and age groups; fish and other seafood are the major sources of PFASs while milk and dairy products dominate in the exposure to PFCAs (EFSA, 2018, 2020).

In early 2000, the principal manufacturing industry started a voluntary phase-out of certain long-chain PFAS, such as PFOS, PFOA, and their precursors (3M Company, 2000, USEPA, 2006). In Europe, the marketing and use of PFOS and its precursors were restricted by the REACH regulation (EC/1907/2006) from 2008, followed by adding them to the EU's POP regulation (EC) 850/2004 in 2010 and later to its recast version, i.e., Regulation (EU) 2019/1021. PFOA and its precursors were attached to the REACH regulation in 2017 (and later to the revised POP regulation), and restrictions have been gradually taking effect since 2020. Moreover, around 200 long-chain PFCAs (C9-14) and their precursors were added to the REACH regulation in 2021. Consequently, the production and use of long-chain PFAS have significantly decreased, but many homologous substances have substituted them, including short-chain PFAAs, such as perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS) and perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), and per- and poly-fluoroalkyl ether carboxylic acids (PFECAs), such as hexafluoropropylene oxide-dimer acid (HFPO-DA) and ammonium 4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoic acid (ADONA) (Wang et al., 2013, Bernardini et al., 2021, ITRC, 2023). Therefore, in early 2023 five EU member states prepared a restriction proposal to the European Chemical Agency (ECHA) covering the production, marketing, and use of all PFAS in the EU (ECHA, 2023).

Despite the regulatory restrictions and voluntary phase-outs, releases of legacy PFAS into water bodies from contaminated sites (e.g., sites with historical use of PFAS containing firefighting foams), landfills and wastewater treatment plants will continue for a long time (Washington et al., 2019, Reinikainen et al., 2022). Moreover, a myriad of other PFAS is still manufactured and used in multiple applications while some of the compounds restricted in the EU are produced in other parts of the world and imported into the European market (Glüge et al., 2020, Joerss and Menger, 2023). Consequently, the spreading of PFAS to the environment from both point and diffuse sources, including atmospheric deposition, is expected to continue even if the proposed, comprehensive EU-level ban will eventually take effect. Hence, preventing future emissions and managing current contamination of PFAS as well as its associated risks to human health and the environment need to be considered in the relevant regulatory frameworks. In the EU, such considerations have recently been addressed by amending several existing legal instruments with new PFAS decision benchmarks. This development reflects the rapidly evolving scientific data on PFAS and manifests itself in a wide range of regulated substances and their benchmark levels, also demonstrating the changing focus from single chemicals to specific PFAS mixtures (Cousins et al., 2020).

The above-mentioned regulatory instruments and policy proposals for the use restriction of PFAS support the ambitions of the EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Action Plan and their associated vision for a toxic-free environment (EC, 2021). These ambitions also relate to a variety of generic policy objectives regarding the regulatory risk assessment of chemicals, such as the 'one-substance one-assessment' (OS-OA) approach, which aims at a more integrated and holistic assessment of individual chemicals and better coordination between the relevant EU agencies. The premise for the OS-OA approach is that when a chemical safety assessment is proposed under one piece of EU legislation, the same assessment shall also be considered under other legal frameworks that regulate the same chemical (EC, 2020a).

Moreover, the EU legitimately emphasizes transparency and science-based approaches in its regulatory procedures on evaluating chemical risks alongside the more generic principles for promoting the accessibility and usability of scientific data (EC, 2019, 2020a, 2022). Incorporating these policy objectives and approaches into practice for PFAS, alongside other persistent and ubiquitous chemicals, in a coherent manner amid constantly evolving regulatory and scientific domains is a challenge that needs attention.

In this study, we critically review the latest European development in the regulatory risk assessment of PFAS, focusing on the comparison and analysis of selected EU thresholds issued for these substances, i.e., levels of PFAS exposure or concentration in environmental media that are considered as safe or that trigger specific management actions. We demonstrate weaknesses and inconsistencies in the current risk-based approaches to PFAS and provide outlooks for their improvement. To our knowledge, this is the first scientific paper on this specific topic. Hence, we believe that our study will stimulate the necessary dialogue on the regulation of environmental PFAS and support the development of more coherent and sound risk and management of these chemicals both in Europe and elsewhere.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Methodology, boundaries, and data sources

The study is based on a comparative analysis of regulatory PFAS thresholds recently set or proposed for assessing and managing the quality of surface water and groundwater, drinking water, and certain foodstuffs in the EU, also considering the tolerable human intake value used to derive some of the concentration thresholds (Table 1). To analyze the coherence of the thresholds, we conducted deterministic calculations based on established risk models and parameter values compiled from public databases and literature (Section 2.3). Background information on the thresholds (Section 2.2) was adopted directly from the relevant EU directives and regulations, and their supporting documents.

The studied thresholds include the current and proposed (draft) environmental quality standards of the Priority Substances Directive 2008/105/EC, the quality standards of the Drinking Water Directive (EU) 2020/2184, the maximum levels in food according to the Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/2388, and the tolerable weekly intake value set by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). The analysis is limited to PFAS thresholds designed for safeguarding human health as being the primary protection target identified within the studied regulatory contexts. This delimitation, i.e., excluding thresholds that focus on ecological risks, also enables meaningful comparison of the thresholds.

2.2. Studied EU thresholds

This section summarizes background information on the PFAS thresholds covered in the study (Table 1). More details on the topic are provided in Supplementary Information (SI).

2.2.1. Tolerable daily/weekly intake

The Tolerable Daily or Weekly Intake (TDI/TWI) is an estimate of the amount of a non-intentionally added substance in food or drinking water that can be consumed daily or weekly over a lifetime without causing an appreciable health risk. In 2020, the EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) re-evaluated its previous scientific opinions (EFSA, 2008; 2018; SI Section 1.1) and issued a new TWI of 4.4 ng/kg_{bw} per week for the sum of PFOA, PFOS, perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), and perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS) (EFSA, 2020). From a human observational study on immunosuppression (Abraham et al., 2020), the lowest benchmark dose (BMDL10) for decreased vaccine antibodies in serum (17.5 ng_{ΣPFAS4}/mL) was derived for one-year-old infants. Using

Table 1

EU thresholds for PFAS concerning tolerable human intake and maximum concentrations in food, surface water, groundwater and drinking water. TWI/TDI = Tolerable Weekly/Daily Intake; (AA)-EQS = (Annual Average) Environmental Quality Standard; GWQS = Groundwater Quality Standard; DWQS = Drinking Water Quality Standard; ML = Maximum Level of contaminant in food (food categories are described in detail in the Annex of Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/2388).

Threshold	Unit	Subject	PFOS	PFOA	PFNA	PFHxS	ΣPFAS 4 ¹⁾	ΣPFAS 20 ²⁾	Total PFAS ³⁾	ΣPFAS 24 ⁴⁾ (RPF)*	Reference
TWI/TDI	ng/kg _{bw} per week/d	Human exposure	–	–	–	–	4,4 / 0,63	–	–	–	EFSA, 2020
AA-EQS	ng/L	Surface water	0,65	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	EU, 2013
EQS biota	µg/kg _{ww}	Surface water	9,1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	EU, 2013
AA-EQS draft	ng/L	Surface water	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	4,4	EC, 2022
EQS biota draft	µg/kg _{ww}	Surface water	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0,077	EC, 2022
GWQS draft	ng/L	Groundwater	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	4,4	EC, 2022
DWQS, sum	ng/L	Drinking water	–	–	–	–	–	100	–	–	EU, 2020
DWQS, total	ng/L	Drinking water	–	–	–	–	–	–	500	–	EU, 2020
ML	µg/kg _{ww}	Eggs	1	0,3	0,7	0,3	1,7	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Fish, cat. 1 (eg. tuna)	2	0,2	0,5	0,2	2	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Fish, cat. 2 (eg. wild salmon)	7	1	2,5	0,2	8	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Fish, cat. 3 (eg. perch)	35	8	8	1,5	45	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Crustaceans	3	0,7	1	1,5	5	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Meat, cat. 1 (bovines, pig, poultry)	0,3	0,8	0,2	0,2	1,3	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Meat, cat. 2 (sheep)	1	0,2	0,2	0,2	1,6	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Meat, cat. 3 (offal of bovines, pig and poultry)	6	0,7	0,4	0,5	8	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Meat, cat. 4 (game animals)	5	3,5	1,5	0,6	9	–	–	–	EU, 2022
		Meat, cat. 5 (offal of game)	50	25	45	3	50	–	–	–	EU, 2022

* Refers to the sum of 24 PFAS expressed as PFOA toxicity equivalent based on the Relative Potency Factors (RPFs), see below in footnote 4. ¹⁾ Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), Perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) and Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS). ²⁾ Perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), Perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA), Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), Perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), PFOA, PFNA, Perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), Perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA), Perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoDA), Perfluorotridecanoic acid (PFTrDA), Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS), Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid (PFPeS), PFHxS, Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid (PFHpS), PFOS, Perfluorononane sulfonic acid (PFNS), Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid (PFDS), Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid (PFUnDS), Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid (PFDoDS) and Perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid (PFTrDS). ³⁾ This value will apply once technical guidelines for monitoring this parameter are developed in accordance with Article 13(7) of the Directive EU/2020/2184. Member States may then decide to use either one or both of the parameters 'PFAS total' or 'PFAS sum' (\sum PFAS₂₀). ⁴⁾ PFOA (RPF 1), PFOS (RPF 2), PFHxS (RPF 0,6), PFNA (RPF 10), PFBS (RPF 0,001), PFHxA (RPF 0,01), PFBA (RPF 0,05), PFPeA (RPF 0,03), PFPeS (RPF 0,3005), PFDA (RPF 7), PFDoDA (RPF 3), PFUnDA (RPF 4), PFHpA (RPF 0,505), PFTrDA (RPF 1,65), PFHpS (RPF 1,3), PFDS (RPF 2), Perfluorotetradecanoic acid (PFTeDA) (RPF 0,3), Perfluorohexadecanoic acid (PFHxDA) (RPF 0,02), Perfluorooctadecanoic acid (PFODA) (RPF 0,02), Ammonium perfluoro (2-methyl-3-oxahexanoate) (HFPO-DA or Gen X) (RPF 0,06), Propanoic Acid / Ammonium 2,2,3-trifluoro-3-(1,1,2,2,3,3-hexafluoro-3-(trifluoromethoxy)propoxy)propanoate (ADONA) (RPF 0,03), 2-(Perfluorohexyl)ethyl alcohol (6:2 FTOH) (RPF 0,02), 2-(Perfluorooctyl)ethanol (8:2 FTOH) (RPF 0,04) and Acetic acid / 2,2-difluoro-2-((2,2,4,5-tetrafluoro-5-(trifluoromethoxy)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl)oxy)-ammonium salt (C6O4) (RPF 0,06).

BPBK modelling and assuming 12 months of breastfeeding, that \sum PFAS4 level in children's serum was estimated to correspond to a long-term maternal exposure of 0.63 ng/kg_{bw}/d (TDI) based on which the TWI was established (EFSA, 2020).

EFSA's TDI/TWI values are not legally binding thresholds *per se*, but they are used to support risk management decisions on the protection of consumers from exposure to contaminants via foodstuffs in the EU policy frameworks.

2.2.2. Environmental quality standards for water and biota

The EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC, later WFD) requires the setting of Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for priority substances to be used in the assessment and monitoring of European water bodies, covering their average annual concentration (AA-EQS) in surface water as well as their concentration in biota (EQS biota; applied for fish) and groundwater (GWQS). The current AA-EQS (0.65 ng/L) and EQS biota for PFOS (9.1 µg/kg_{ww}) are both based on estimated risks to human health upon consumption of fishery products (115 g/d), using the EFSA's TDI form 2008 as the toxicological reference value and allowing for 10 % allocation of the TDI to fish ingestion (SI Section 1.2). A proposal for new EQSs that would replace the current values for PFOS was issued in 2022 (EC, 2022). The proposed EQS biota (0.0077 µg/kg_{ww}; applied for fish) was derived by applying the same methodology as in the case of the current EQS but replacing the EFSA's previous TDI value for PFOS with the new group TDI for \sum PFAS4 and using 20 % allocation of the TDI to fish intake. The proposed new AA-EQS in surface water (4.4 ng/L) as well the proposed quality standard in groundwater (GWQS; 4.4 ng/L) also rely on the EFSA's new TDI for \sum PFAS4 but they are based on drinking water consumption (2 L/d) instead of fish ingestion. Moreover, the proposed new EQSs and GWQS are each expressed as a PFOA toxicity equivalent by applying relative potency factors (RPFs) of 24 PFAS (Table 1) based on liver toxicity in rodents (Bil et al., 2021).

2.2.3. Drinking water standards

The EU Drinking Water Directive (EU/2020/2184, later DWD) aims to safeguard human health and regulates the quality of all water intended for human consumption. The DWD sets drinking water quality standards (DWQS) for the sum of twenty selected PFAS and total PFAS (Table 1). The latter value will only apply once technical guidelines for monitoring this parameter are developed and the EU member states may then decide to use either one or both parameters.

The DWQSs are generally based on the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) and its guidelines for drinking water quality as described in Directive 98/83/EC (EU, 1998). However, we did not find any publicly available documentation on how the current DWQSs for PFAS have been derived (SI Section 1.3).

2.2.4. Maximum contaminant levels in food

Amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 on setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs (EU, 2006b), the new Regulation (EU) 2022/2388 issued corresponding thresholds for PFAS (EU, 2022). The maximum contaminant levels (ML) apply to the edible part of food including processed and mixed food products. Food items with levels of contaminants higher than the MLs may not be sold or placed on the market.

The MLs for PFAS were established separately for the concentrations of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS as well as their sum, and for ten different foodstuff categories, including fish and seafood, eggs, meat, and offal (Table 1). We did not find information specifically on the foundation of those MLs. However, according to the recitals of Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006, the MLs should be toxicologically acceptable but also reasonably achievable. Moreover, according to the EFSA, the MLs, in general, are set around the 90th percentile of background concentrations in different food items, following the principle of 'strict but feasible' (Fürst et al., 2019; SI Section 1.4).

2.3. Health risk assessment

To illustrate and compare the level of health protection embedded in each PFAS concentration threshold, we employed generic, established exposure and risk models for the oral route (Eq. 1–3). To enable justified comparison of the thresholds, we assumed that each threshold for PFAS sum concentrations consisted solely of four compounds as per the EFSA's TWI/TDI value, which is currently the only EU-wide health-based reference value. All these four compounds (i.e., PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS) are included in each sum threshold used in the comparison.

First, we calculated the average daily doses of \sum PFAS4 (ADD \sum PFAS4; ng/kg_{bw}/day) via ingested water, fish and other foodstuffs (in accordance with the food categories of Regulation (EU) 2022/2388; Table 1) at concentrations (µg/L or µg/kg) equal to the relevant threshold values (TV), i.e., the DWQSs, the draft AA-EQS and GWQS, the current and draft EQS biota (note that the current EQS is only applied to PFOS), and the MLs, assuming default ingestion rates (IR_{water}, L/d; IR_{food}, g/d) and a body weight of an adult consumer (BW = 70 kg):

$$ADD_{\sum PFAS4, water} = TV \times IR_{water} \times 10^{-3} / BW \quad (1a)$$

$$ADD_{\sum PFAS4, food} = TV \times IR_{food} / BW \quad (1b)$$

The ingestion rates of drinking water and different foodstuffs (IR_{water} and IR_{food}) were derived from the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database (EFSA, 2022), also considering the EU default values for fish (115 g/d) and drinking water (2L/d) consumption. These ingestion rates correspond to the mean 95th percentile values (p95) and the average values of the daily consumption by the European adult population (Table S2). An equal fish ingestion rate was used for all three fish categories of the relevant MLs since the EFSA database does not separate different fish species as per Regulation (EU) 2022/2388 and the EQS biota similarly applies to all fish species. More details about the selection of the ingestion rates are provided in the [Supplementary Information \(SI Section 2\)](#).

We estimated a theoretical health risk associated with each threshold using the Hazard Quotient (HQ), by comparing the calculated ADDs (Eq. 1) to the EFSA's TDI value (0.63 ng/kg_{bw}/day; Eq. (2)). When HQ < 1, no significant risk of adverse health effects is expected, while HQ > 1 indicates that such effects are possible.

$$HQ = ADD_{\sum PFAS4} / TDI \quad (2)$$

Next, we calculated the maximum allowable daily amounts of drinking water and foodstuffs (IR_{max}; L/d or g/d) that an adult person (BW = 70 kg) could safely consume as per the EFSA's TDI, assuming that \sum PFAS4 concentrations in the consumed water and foodstuffs were equal to the relevant thresholds:

$$IR_{max, water} = TDI \times BW / DWQS \times 10^{-3} \quad (3a)$$

$$IR_{max, food} = TDI \times BW / ML \quad (3b)$$

Finally, we compared the calculated IR_{max} values to the EU p95 and mean consumption of drinking water and corresponding foodstuffs and determined the equivalent number of servings (or eggs) one could safely consume per month, assuming an average portion of 150 g for the different food items, and 55 g for one egg (Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, 2023).

The methodology used in the calculations (Eq. 1–3) corresponds to the derivation of the current and proposed EQSs (JRC, 2022), and the WHO's guidelines for drinking water quality (WHO, 2022), by presuming a continuous daily consumption of PFAS-containing food or water and 100 % bioavailability for the ingested PFAS in the gastrointestinal tract as per a conservative approach. We deliberately excluded the allocation factors used to derive the EQSs (see Section 2.2.2 and SI Section 1.2) from our main calculations, so that we could coherently compare the level of health risk associated with each threshold as such.

Fig. 1. Health risk estimates (Hazard Quotient, HQ) for oral exposure to \sum PFAS4 (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS; or solely PFOS in the case of the current EQS biota) at concentrations corresponding to the current and proposed regulatory thresholds for food and water. The bars illustrate HQs calculated with the EU p95 ingestion rates while the symbol (◆) shows the HQs calculated with the EU mean ingestion rates. When $HQ < 1$, no significant risk of adverse health effects is expected, while $HQ > 1$ indicates that such effects are possible. DWQS = Drinking Water Quality Standard; GWQS = Groundwater Quality Standard; (AA-)EQS = (Annual Average) Environmental Quality Standard.

We do, however, address the role of the allocation factors in the complementary risk estimates and discussion (Sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3). Moreover, our comparative health risk assessment does not cover the current AA-EQS for surface water (0.65 ng/L; Table 1) which, unlike the other thresholds, is not based on direct human exposure (see Section 2.2.2 and SI Section 1.2).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Quantitative comparison of the thresholds

The theoretical health risk associated with the different PFAS thresholds varies dramatically, as presented in Fig. 1. The estimated range of oral exposure to \sum PFAS4 at concentrations corresponding to the thresholds (i.e., $ADD_{\sum PFAS4}$; Eq. 1) is 0.13–73.9 and 0.01–17.3 ng/kg_{bw}/day, based on the EU p95 and mean ingestion rates. Thus, the respective health risk estimates, i.e., HQ values (Eq. (2)), vary from 0,02

(for ingestion of game animals’ offal based on the EU mean consumption) to 120 (for ingestion of perch and white fish based on the EU p95 consumption). The broad range of HQs is partly explained by the variation in the estimated consumption of different foodstuffs. Hence, the low health risk estimates associated with the MLs for the meat of sheep and game animals, offal, and crustaceans, arise from their lower ingestion rates compared to fish and meat of bovines, pig, and poultry (Table 2). The high health risk estimates associated with the MLs for fish, on the other hand, are partly explained by using the same fish ingestion rate for all three fish categories (Table 2). It is noteworthy, however, that the health risk estimate associated with the maximum authorised ML in fish at the EU p95 ingestion rate (i.e., $HQ = 120$; ML fish cat. 3) exceeds 600-fold the corresponding risk estimate of the draft EQS biota. The allocation factor of 20 % used in the setting of the draft EQS biota (SI Section 1.2) compared to the 100 % allocation we employed in our calculations, explains this difference only partly. As for drinking water, equivalent comparison between the DWQSs and the draft AA-EQS/

Table 2

Maximum allowable daily ingestion of certain foodstuffs ($IR_{\max, \text{food}}$) and drinking water ($IR_{\max, \text{water}}$) as per the EFSA's TDI in comparison with the EU p95 and mean consumption for adults (IR, EU p95; IR, EU mean), and the corresponding number of servings (or eggs) one could safely consume per month assuming an average portion of 150 g for the different food items, and 55 g for one egg. EU ingestion rates exceeding the estimated IR_{\max} values are presented in bold.

Foodstuff	$IR_{\max, \text{food}}^* \text{ g/d}$	IR, EU p95 g/d	IR, EU mean g/d	Maximum number of eggs (55 g) or fish/meat servings (150 g) per month
Eggs	25.9	80	20	14.6
Fish, cat.1 (e.g., tuna, cod)	22.1	115¹⁾	27	4.6
Fish, cat.2 (e.g., wild salmon, herring)	5.5	115¹⁾	27	1.1
Fish, cat.3 (e.g., perch, whitefish)	0.98	115¹⁾	27	0.2 (2.4 per year)
Crustaceans	8.8	7.0	0.59	1.8
Bovine, pig, poultry (meat, cat.1)	34	316	141	7.0
Sheep (meat, cat.2)	28	24	2.6	5.7
Offal (meat, cat. 3)	5.5	5.2	0.27	1.1
Game (meat, cat. 4)	4.90	8.3	0.48	1.0
Game offal (meat, cat. 5)	0.88	0.83	0.02	0.2 (2.2 per year)
Drinking water	$IR_{\max, \text{water}}^{**} \text{ L/d}$	Intake, EU p95 L/d	Intake, EU mean L/d	Maximum number of water glasses (2 dL) per day
Drinking water, sum of 20 PFAS	0.44	2²⁾	0.956	2.2
Drinking water, total PFAS	0.09	2²⁾	0.956	0.4

* $IR_{\max, \text{food}} = \text{TDI} (0.63 \text{ ng/kg}_{\text{bw}}/\text{d}) * \text{BW} (70 \text{ kg}) / \text{ML}$.

** $IR_{\max, \text{water}} = \text{TDI} (0.63 \text{ ng/kg}_{\text{bw}}/\text{d}) * \text{BW} (70 \text{ kg}) / \text{DWQS} * 10^{-3}$.

¹⁾ EU default; the corresponding actual p95 value from the EFSA database is 114 g/d (EFSA, 2022).

²⁾ EU default; the corresponding actual p95 value from the EFSA database is 2.1 L/d (EFSA, 2022).

GWQS results in 4.5- and 23-fold health risk estimates for the $DWQS_{\text{sum}}$ and $DWQS_{\text{total}}$, respectively, assuming that the concentration in drinking water consisted solely of $\sum \text{PFAS4}$.

The difference in health protection built into each threshold is even bigger if we consider PFAS concentrations individually instead of $\sum \text{PFAS4}$ (Fig. 2A). The difference in approaches adopted to characterize the risks of PFAS to human health in the relevant regulations (Section 2.2) explains this gap. Regarding fish (Fig. 2A), the maximum MLs (Table 1) are 910 (PFOS) and 1040 (PFNA) times higher than the corresponding draft EQSs for biota expressed in PFOA toxicity equivalents, i.e., 0.0385 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{ww}}$ ($\text{RPF}_{\text{PFOS}} = 2$) and 0.0077 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{ww}}$ ($\text{RPF}_{\text{PFNA}} = 10$), assuming PFOS or PFNA would be the only detectable PFAS in fish. Considerable variation also emerges between the $DWQS_{\text{sum}}$ and the proposed AA-EQS/GWQS (Fig. 2B). If measurable concentrations of the $\sum \text{PFAS20}$ in drinking water covered only individual substances, a concentration below 100 ng/L for any of the 20 PFAS included in the $DWQS_{\text{sum}}$ would meet the threshold, while a concentration exceeding 100 ng/L would not. In the case of the proposed AA-EQS or GWQS, a measured PFBS concentration of 100 ng/L, corresponding to 0.1 ng/L in PFOA equivalent, would be 44 times lower than the proposed EQS while the same measured concentration for PFNA, corresponding to 1000 ng/L in PFOA equivalent, would exceed the threshold around 230-fold.

The theoretical maximum allowable daily consumption rates, IR_{\max} , of fish, meat (bovine, pig and poultry), and drinking water, based on the EFSA's TDI (Eq. 3), are notably lower than the actual average consumption of those foodstuffs in Europe (Table 2). In comparison with the EU p95 ingestion rates, the IR_{\max} values are also exceeded for eggs and game animals' meat. For example, the IR_{\max} of perch at a concentration equal to its relevant ML (fish cat. 3) would be one gram, i.e., less than 4 % of the average European daily fish consumption (27 g/d). Considering a normal serving of 150 g fish per meal, one could thus safely consume only two meals of perch per year, even without considering additional dietary sources or other background exposure. Moreover, if the concentrations of $\sum \text{PFAS4}$ in drinking water were equal to the $DWQS$ s, the theoretical maximum allowable daily consumption of water without considering background exposure would be 0.44 L/d ($DWQS_{\text{sum}}$) and 0.09 L/d ($DWQS_{\text{total}}$), corresponding roughly to two glasses or half a glass of water (2 dL) per day. This value is clearly below the mean EU consumption or the recommended daily water intake (e.g., Armstrong et al., 2018).

3.2. Considerations on the scientific foundation of the thresholds

3.2.1. The new tolerable weekly intake

The understanding of tolerable human exposure to PFAS has changed dramatically based on the progress of the EFSA's TDI/TWI values (EFSA, 2008, 2018, 2020). From 2008 to 2020, the decrease in the TDI/TWI for PFOS and PFOA has been 238- and 2380-fold, respectively, assuming the concentration of $\sum \text{PFAS4}$ as per the new TWI consisted only of PFOS or PFOA; Fig. 3. The major determinant in this development is that the most recent and stringent values are based on epidemiological observations contrary to the previous values that were derived from animal studies. Hence, the toxicological endpoints considered in deriving the values have changed and are not fully commensurable.

The key epidemiological study on which the current TWI is founded demonstrated a statistically significant association between the levels of PFOA in the plasma of one-year-old breastfed children and decreased levels of vaccine antibodies against influenza, tetanus, and diphtheria (Abraham et al., 2019). The same association was not found for PFOS, PFNA, or PFHxS, nor was any relationship observed between the measured levels of PFAS in plasma and the number of infections within the group of children studied although the $\sum \text{PFAS4}$ concentrations in plasma were substantially higher than the BMDL (17.5 ng/mL) applied in deriving the TWI. Similarly, no association between maternal exposure to PFOA and infections in children was observed in a case of high exposure to PFOA-contaminated drinking water (Frisbee et al., 2009, C8 Science Panel, 2012, Looker et al., 2014). A relatively considerable number of studies, however, report that exposure to PFOA is associated with immune response, but evidence of a causal link between exposure and increased risk of infectious diseases is lacking or is inconsistent (ATSDR, 2020, Chang et al., 2016, Steenland et al., 2020). Moreover, based on extensive literature reviews (Fenton et al., 2021, Kirk et al., 2018, Chohan et al., 2020, Steenland et al., 2020), many studies have found a probable connection between exposure to PFAS and some adverse health outcomes, but usually at substantially higher levels than the EFSA's current TWI (e.g., Andersson et al., 2019, Manea et al., 2020). Resulting from the ubiquitous occurrence of PFAS in the environment, even the mean dietary background exposure to all age groups in the European population (median of the mean lower bound exposure: 0.86 to 4.87 $\text{ng}/\text{kg}_{\text{bw}}/\text{d}$) is estimated to exceed the TWI (EFSA, 2020). On the other hand, based on biomonitoring studies both in Europe and the United States (USA), human exposure to the sum of PFOS, PFOA,

Fig. 2. Variability of the concentration thresholds for selected PFAS assuming each of these would be the only detectable PFAS in fish (A) or water (B). EQS biota, AA-EQS and GWQS expressed as PFOA toxicity equivalents applying the Relative Potency Factors (RPSs) as per Bil et al. (2021): $RPF_{PFOA} = 1$, $RPF_{PFOS} = 2$, $RPF_{PFHxS} = 0.6$, $RPF_{PFNA} = 10$, $RPF_{PFBS} = 0.001$. DWQS = Drinking water quality standard; GWQS = Groundwater Quality Standard; (AA-)EQS = (Annual Average-) Environmental Quality Standard; ML = Maximum Level in food. Fish cat. 3 refers to fish species specified in Regulation (EU) 2022/2388, such as perch and whitefish.

Fig. 3. Development of the EFSA's Tolerable Daily/Weekly Intake values. The 2020 value refers to the sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, and PFHxS.

PFNA, and PFHxS has significantly decreased since early 2000 particularly due to the phase-out of PFOS (Haug et al., 2009, Schröter-Kermani et al., 2013, Liu et al., 2015).

Despite the uncertainties concerning the actual health risks associated with exposure to low levels of PFAS, immunological effects, such as reduced vaccine antibodies, due to any environmental contaminant should be considered of concern, at least at the population level (Abraham et al., 2019). Thus, the EFSA's current TWI may be justified in its policy context and as per the precautionary principle. Nevertheless, it seems legitimate to question whether such a rigorous value –below the average European background exposure – is an appropriate threshold for defining maximum concentrations of substances that are ubiquitous in the environment. Furthermore, the scientific basis of the TWI does not indisputably indicate an increased probability of adverse health effects at this exposure level, nor even a correlation with the vaccine antibodies in the case of three of the four PFAS covered by the threshold. In fact, a recent international collaboration effort focusing on safe dose levels for PFOA, concluded that immune suppression, including vaccine response, as the critical endpoint at typical serum concentrations of PFAS is not of clinical relevance due to a wide range of potential confounders, and that the current epidemiologic data does not constitute a reliable basis for determining a scientifically sound reference value for PFOA to be used in human health risk assessment (Burgoon et al., 2023). Burgoon et al. (2023) further concluded, based on animal studies, that a reasonable estimate of a protective intake level for PFOA is in the range of 10–70

ng/kg_{bw}/day. Moreover, the derivation of the EFSA's TWI value involved conservative assumptions, such as exclusive breastfeeding for the first 12 months of the infant. To avoid setting risk-based thresholds that are too cautious, one should always try to find the right balance between their scientific justifications and their feasibility in terms of realistic risk management (see Section 3.3.4).

3.2.2. Proposed environmental quality standards for surface water and groundwater

Regarding their scientific foundation, the proposed EQSs for biota and water (including the AA-EQS and GWQS), resting upon theoretical estimates on human exposure via ingestion of fish or drinking water (Section 2.2.2), are the only concentration thresholds in line with the EFSA's current TWI value. On the other hand, this can challenge their reasonable application. Based on extensive monitoring campaigns across European surface water bodies (Carvalho et al., 2016, EFSA, 2020, JRC, 2022), it seems effectively impossible to find wild fish with a measured \sum PFAS4 concentration below the draft EQS biota. For example, the lower bound average concentrations of PFOS in all fish species in a large European dataset were orders of magnitude higher (i.e., 0.16–14.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{ww}}$; EFSA, 2020) than the proposed EQS. Similarly, in a Finnish fish monitoring dataset of pooled samples of perch and Baltic herring from inland waters and the Baltic Sea, also covering remote locations without local pollution sources, the measured PFOS concentration in fish meat was below the draft EQS biota in only one sample and even the 1st percentile of the dataset (0.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{ww}}$; n = 89) exceeded this threshold (Finnish Environment Institute, 2023). Using the previous datasets, the exceedance of the proposed EQS biota would be even greater as per the RPF approach (Section 3.3.3), which doubles the significance of the measured concentration of PFOS in comparison with the EQS (i.e., $\text{RPF}_{\text{PFOS}} = 2$). PFOS concentrations have also been shown to exceed the draft EQS biota in several market basket fish, although their PFAS levels are generally lower than in wild fish; in fact, such a low threshold cannot even be reliably achieved due to analytical limitations (e.g., Ruffe et al., 2020). Hence, the application of the proposed EQS biota in case-specific decision-making may be restricted to using it as a long-term objective for monitoring programs instead of adopting it as a trigger for actual risk management measures.

As for surface water, the proposed AA-EQS is around seven times higher than the current AA-EQS due to the change in the basis for deriving the value, i.e., focusing on drinking water intake instead of fish consumption. The need for generating a threshold that is achievable in practice may have been one of the triggers of this change, notwithstanding that even the draft AA-EQS is commonly exceeded in European surface waters (JRC, 2022). Using the same methodology and the same input parameters as in the case of deriving the current AA-EQS, i.e., back-calculation from the EQS biota for PFOS to corresponding PFOS concentration in water and adopting a fixed bioaccumulation factor (Section 2.2.2 and SI Section 1.2), the proposed AA-EQS would become distinctly lower (0.0056 ng/L) than the typical analytical detection limits for any PFAS (e.g., Brunn et al., 2023). The use of a fixed bioaccumulation factor for the group of the four PFAS covered by the TWI, on the other hand, is scientifically unjustified due to the different bioaccumulation potential of the individual four compounds (SCHEER, 2022).

Both the proposed and the current EQS biota are based on conservative parameters that are not fully representative of the whole of Europe and are therefore likely to overestimate the exposure of the general population in most regions. The applied fish ingestion rate of 115 g/d corresponds to the mean 95th percentile value of European adults in the EFSA database (SI Section 2). Based on the same dataset (Table S2), the mean European consumption (mean value based on all the surveys) is 27 g/d, which is roughly four times lower than the default ingestion rate. The mean daily consumption of fish in the individual surveys ranges from 8.8 to 76 g/d and remains below the European average consumption in 15 out of 25 countries. Considering only adults

that eat fish or seafood and the most recent national surveys in the EFSA database, the mean European consumption (23–108 g/d with an average value of 71 g/d) is also below the default fish intake rate. It should also be noted that in practice, the EQS biota is only applied to locally caught wild fish, whose contribution to national fish consumption rates varies in each EU member state. In 2019, the EU self-sufficiency in fish and seafood was 41 % (EUMOFA, 2021), showing that more than half of the consumption, on average, rests on imported fish products. Moreover, the contribution of farmed fish and seafood, such as mussels, salmon, and trout, to overall consumption of fishery products is significant in many countries (EC, 2018), while several studies indicate that PFAS concentrations in farmed fish are significantly lower than in wild fish (Koponen et al., 2015, Zafeiraki et al., 2019, Young et al., 2022). Therefore, both the fish ingestion rate and the allocation factor applied for deriving the EQS biota could justifiably be modified at national level. In Finland, for example, the average intake of fish from local natural waters was 8.2 g_{ww}/d in 2021, representing around 24 % of the total mean fish consumption (Natural Resources Institute Finland, 2023). Using these average national data instead of the EU default values, a justified EQS biota in Finland (applying Eq. (3a)) could be around 1.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}_{\text{ww}}$, i.e., nearly 17 times higher than the draft EQS. However, even this nationally modified value would often be exceeded in wild fish, especially for PFOS, and it would be significantly lower than the highest current MLs for fish.

3.2.3. Drinking water standard

It seems likely that the DWQSs for PFAS do not have an unequivocal scientific foundation but instead, they have been issued at least partly on the grounds of a political agreement (SI Section 1.3). Acknowledging the ubiquitous presence of PFAS in the environment as well as numerous findings on contaminated drinking water sources (e.g., Jian et al., 2017), it is probable that also the technical and economic feasibility of achieving a given concentration level has been considered in the setting of the DWQSs, like in the case of many other drinking water contaminants (WHO, 2022). Despite these considerations, one would expect that the DWQSs in their relevant regulatory context, were based on the most up-to-date toxicological data and embedded with adequate conservatism as drinking water can be a major contributor to human exposure to PFAS. Hence, it is surprising that this has not been the case for either of the two DWQSs for PFAS, given that at the time of their publication, at least the EFSA's TWIs for PFOS and PFOA from 2018 had already been established. Based on these thresholds, the risk-based value for PFOA in drinking water, for example, would be around 6 ng/L ($\text{TDI} = 0.86 \text{ ng}/\text{kg}_{\text{bw}}/\text{d}$; applying Eq. (3a) and using the default allocation factor of 20 %). The DWQS for total PFAS seems to include a precautionary element, however, considering there are no toxicological data available for most PFAS, and many compounds are likely to be less toxic than, for example, PFOS and PFOA (e.g., Bil et al., 2021). Nevertheless, from the viewpoint of the EFSA's current TWI value, the $\text{DWQS}_{\text{total}}$ is not cautious but extremely high.

The individual PFAS included in the DWQS_{sum} appear to be based on a somewhat random selection of short- and long-chain PFAAs, excluding their commonly used precursors and substitutes, such as FTOHs and PFECAs, some of which are covered by the proposed EQSs and GWQS as per the RPF approach. Thus, the regulation of those specific 20 substances does not seem to have a solid scientific justification. Both parameters, i.e., DWQS_{sum} and $\text{DWQS}_{\text{total}}$, are in line with the EU's desire to regulate PFAS as a group instead of individual compounds (EC, 2020a). A major contradiction is, however, that the valid drinking water standards in the EU are 20–100 times higher than the proposed EQSs for surface water and groundwater, which are based on drinking water intake applying the EFSA's current TWI. Consequently, some EU member states, such as Sweden and Denmark, have issued national threshold values for PFAS in drinking water at concentrations comparable to the draft EQSs (i.e., 2–4 ng/L; SCHEER, 2022). These national thresholds are also in line with the draft national drinking water standards for PFOA (4

ng/L) and PFOS (4 ng/L) in the USA (US EPA, 2023).

3.2.4. Maximum levels in food

Although Regulation (EU) 2022/2388 on the MLs for PFAS in its recitals refers to the EFSA's latest TWI, introduced two years earlier than the MLs were issued, there is obviously no connection between them (Section 3.1). Moreover, the variation between the MLs for different food categories and the individual four PFAS (PFOS, PFHxS, PFOA, and PFNA) is not systematic, indicating that the values reflect the variability between the measured food concentrations rather than the toxicity of specific PFAS or the consumption of different foodstuffs. For example, the MLs for fish are highest, by a large margin, for PFOS, which is more bioaccumulative in fish than the other three PFAS, yet not the least toxic (Smit and Verbruggen, 2022).

The foundation of the MLs is understandable, given that PFAS are ubiquitous, and that a simplistic risk-based approach resting upon the EFSA's current TWI could mean that a substantial part of the foodstuffs currently consumed by the European population, might no longer be authorized to be placed on the market (cf. the proposed EQS biota; Section 3.2.2). This political choice, however, signifies that the MLs are in clear conflict with the EFSA's most recent scientific opinion, although the MLs should be set at levels that are toxicologically acceptable and guarantee a high level of protection for human health (EU, 2006b).

3.3. Overview of methodological and policy considerations on the thresholds

3.3.1. Grouping approaches

Until recently, the regulatory risk assessment of PFAS has focused on single substances, mainly PFOS and PFOA. The emphasis put on individual substances ignores the potential for more severe environmental or health outcomes due to combined toxicity given that different PFAS share similar chemical characteristics and they generally occur in complex mixtures (Cousins et al., 2020). Acknowledging the risk of not being sufficiently protective as well as the impracticability of managing all PFAS individually, the EU has been moving towards regulating PFAS as relevant groups, and therefore all the recent regulatory thresholds for PFAS cover more than one substance. The studied regulatory thresholds, however, apply various means to characterize PFAS mixtures, and thus their interpretation of the toxicity and relevance of individual PFAS differ. In this section, we focus specifically on the RPFs adopted in the case of the draft EQSs and GWQS, while grouping approaches associated with the other thresholds have been discussed in Section 3.2.

The RPF approach applied for the draft EQSs and GWQS presumes that the potency of each designated 24 PFAS to cause immunotoxic effects to humans (as per the EFSA's TWI) is equivalent to its hepatotoxic potency in rats. Although similar differences in the toxic potency of PFAS as those defined by the proposed RPFs have been identified for several endpoints in other studies (Zeilmaker et al., 2018), and corresponding approaches based on toxicity equivalents are applied to other substances, such as polychlorinated dioxins/furans (PCDD/F) and dioxin-like polychlorinated biphenyls (dl-PCB) (Van den Berg et al., 2006, 2013) and organophosphorus pesticides (Bosgra et al., 2009), the suitability of the proposed RPFs for PFAS to represent immunological effects has not been confirmed as stated by their authors (Bil et al., 2021). Moreover, since the association between PFAS exposure and reduced vaccine response in the key study behind the EFSA's TWI value was demonstrated only for PFOA, not PFOS, PFNA, or PFHxS (Abraham et al., 2019), it does not seem justified to presume PFOS to be twice (RPF = 2) and PFNA to be 10 times (RPF = 10) more toxic to the human immune system than PFOA. Furthermore, the RPF approach indicates PFNA's toxicity to be 17-fold compared to PFHxS, although the EFSA's TWI assumes their equal potency. Acknowledging all this and the notion by Bil et al. (2021) that their approach may be used as a risk assessment screening tool, it seems premature to incorporate the proposed RPFs as such into regulatory thresholds. Rietjens et al. (2022) presented similar

arguments in their response to the editor of Bil et al. (2021), claiming that the given RPFs are not yet robust enough to be used in risk assessment and management strategies. Although the RPF approach appears to be a promising way of dealing with PFAS mixtures, the RPFs should first be properly validated (or revised if necessary) to truly represent the immunotoxic effect on humans, assuming immune suppression is to be considered as the most appropriate endpoint for defining a health-based reference value for PFAS in the first place (see Section 3.2.1). Furthermore, data gaps in understanding the toxicokinetics and the most relevant modes of actions or adverse outcome pathways within the large family of PFAS limit a scientifically justified application of any grouping approach for the moment (Deepika et al., 2022, Goodrum et al., 2021). In the long term, all the regulatory thresholds relying on grouping approaches should also cover other environmentally relevant PFAS than those being regulated today, including the current and the potentially coming substitutes of long-chain PFAS.

3.3.2. Coherence and harmonization

Acknowledging the demonstrated variation in the foundation of the studied thresholds, it can be stated that at present, the methodological bases for the regulation and assessment of the health risks of PFAS are neither consistent nor in line with the desirable OS-OA approach. On the other hand, the OS-OA approach is mainly designed to address chemical safety and hazard assessments under various pieces of chemical registration and authorization frameworks, such as the REACH on industrial chemicals, Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 on pesticides, and Directive 2001/83/EC on pharmaceuticals, as well as Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on chemical classification, labeling and packaging (CLP) (van Dijk et al., 2021, EC, 2020a). These frameworks deal with chemical risks in a somewhat theoretical context and aim at preventing them, in which case the management of risks rests upon non-technical approaches such as use restrictions on the chemicals of concern. This means that the risk assessment approaches within the registration and authorization frameworks need to be generic and follow the precautionary principle, which often leads to very conservative risk estimates and decision benchmarks. In other regulatory contexts, for example, related to local industrial emissions or existing environmental contamination, the premise of risk assessment is more case-specific and thus enables or should enable more realistic evidence-based considerations followed by the appropriate 'source-pathway-receptor' linkages and the implementation of technological solutions for risk management (Reinikainen and Sorvari, 2016). Here, socio-economic factors also play a crucial role, as complete prevention of emissions or exposure is often not possible, at least for ubiquitous contaminants such as PFAS. This is also clearly stated, for example, in Regulation (EC) 1881/2006 on setting the MLs for food (EU, 2022) and in the WHO's guidelines on drinking water quality (WHO, 2022) on which the DWQSs are primarily based. Therefore, the relevant receptors and exposure pathways as well as the acceptability or tolerance of chemical risks may legitimately differ between specific regulations. This means that the variation between the regulatory thresholds or their associated scientific foundation is not automatically a sign of contradictory policies despite the generic ambition for the OS-OA approach or harmonization.

Notwithstanding the different starting points for chemical risk assessment in various legal frameworks, the level of environmental and health protection regarding a specific chemical should be equivalent in similar regulatory contexts and circumstances. This is important from the viewpoint of impartiality and a prerequisite for consistent regulatory decisions. As shown in this study, such consistency is lacking between the recently issued PFAS thresholds. The obvious inconsistencies associated with the thresholds are prone to confusing the relevant stakeholders, including the authorities across administrative sectors. Such inconsistencies may also impose unequal or unreasonable demands on different industries and other parties involved depending on whether they are required to comply with the most stringent thresholds or not (e.

g., regulating PFAS in fish according to the water legislation and the proposed EQS biota or as per the food regulations and the MLs) or cause unwarranted risks to public health in regions where PFAS concentrations in food or drinking water are reaching the DWQs or the highest MLs. However, we are not advocating harmonizing all individual thresholds in terms of their concentration levels, but we are calling for consideration to be given to their actual regulatory purpose and the opportunities for implementing reasonable risk management, alongside valid scientific justifications (see Section 3.3.4).

3.3.3. Availability and transparency of background information

To increase trust in its policymaking, the EU has committed to transparent data governance by promoting access and reuse of its data assets across European agencies, national administrations, and other stakeholder groups, such as academia and industry (EC, 2020b). Open data policy and transparency are also key principles in the EU chemical strategy, including the OS-OA approach, which specifically refers to the European food safety sector as a good example of how to implement these principles in the regulatory assessment of chemicals (EC, 2020a). Regulation (EU) 2019/1381 on the transparency and sustainability of the EU risk assessment in the food chain specifically states, for example, that “information should be provided on how risk management decisions were reached and, on the factors, other than the results of the risk assessment, which were considered by the risk managers, as well as how those factors were weighed up against each other”. Similarly, transparency in risk assessment and open risk communication are prerequisites for advancing confidence in any chemical regulation and for optimizing its implementation, including the derivation and application of regulatory thresholds.

The principle of transparency and open communication is successfully incorporated into the setting of the EFSA’s TWI value and the proposed EQSs for PFAS in the form of detailed background documentation. The same statement, however, does not apply to the DWQs nor the MLs issued for PFAS as unambiguous information on their fundamentals is simply not findable or accessible. Even if the rationale behind those thresholds was justifiably not fully risk-based or compatible with the most recent scientific data (see Section 3.3.4), it is unacceptable not to communicate this explicitly to the public and especially to the parties obliged by the relevant regulations. Furthermore, in terms of the MLs, by referring to the EFSA’s scientific opinion and the newest TWI in its recitals, Regulation (EU) 2022/2388 specifically indicates that this toxicological data has been considered in the MLs while it has not. Background information on the thresholds is not only essential in their specific regulatory contexts but also in a broader sense given that the thresholds are often used as benchmarks within the development of national or regional approaches where EU regulations are not in place (e.g., risk assessment and management of contaminated sites). It is therefore paramount that the authorities at different administrative levels know the basis of the thresholds as well as their limitations. Furthermore, such documentation enables monitoring the regulatory development of specific chemicals and risk assessment methodologies concerning the EU’s policy objectives. Hence, we argue that the actual foundation of the DWQs and MLs should be transparently reported to avoid misinterpretation.

3.3.4. Implications for risk management and application of the thresholds

The setting of a contaminant threshold is a risk management decision at the science-policy interface where toxicological or other risk estimates must be coupled with the relevant regulatory objectives and requirements as well as socio-economic and technological considerations, including the environmental occurrence of the contaminants (Petit et al., 2021). For example, when issuing thresholds for contaminants in food and drinking water, socio-economic and technological factors to be considered may include the balance between health risks and the benefits of consuming a specific foodstuff, the technical or economic feasibility of the food production chain or water treatment, and the analytical limitations for achieving low concentrations (EU, 2006b; WHO, 2022).

In the context of PFAS thresholds, socio-economic factors associated with the ubiquitous presence of PFAS seem to have affected the MLs and DWQs, while the proposed EQSs and GWQs were set directly based on toxicological risk assessment. In the latter case, selecting drinking water use as the basis for the draft AA-EQS may have been due to practical considerations, however.

Considering potential case-specific risk management measures associated with the application of the PFAS thresholds, particularly the proposed EQS biota is unnecessarily low and likely to be unattainable. For example, applying the proposed EQS biota in national monitoring programs would mean that most of the surface water bodies in Europe would probably fail to meet the policy goal of a good chemical status as per the WFD, resulting mainly from the bioaccumulation of PFOS in fish (Rüdel et al., 2022). The same holds already true for polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), whose use and production in the EU have also been restricted (Eljarrat and Barcelo, 2018). From the socio-economic perspective, the EQSs should thus acknowledge the widely elevated background concentrations (i.e., concentrations resulting from diffuse sources, such as atmospheric deposition) of legacy PFAS across the European surface waters as seems to have been done in the case of the MLs, both for PFAS and other widespread contaminants. However, contrary to setting fixed thresholds derived from the EU-wide occurrence data, the application of the EQSs in their regulatory context should allow consideration of national or regional background concentrations of PFAS, despite their anthropogenic origin. This stems from the conclusion that the ubiquitous presence of PFAS is a fact that cannot be overlooked or avoided by any regulatory obligation as in the case of naturally occurring elements. Hence, the EQSs derived by relevant risk assessment could only apply in circumstances where the national, regional, or local background concentration is lower than the risk-based value. This would mean that the measured concentrations would be compared to a representative background level instead of the very low risk-based EQS. A similar approach is already incorporated into the application of the EQSs of metals if their natural background concentrations prevent compliance with the thresholds (EU, 2008). Moreover, the same principle applies to the setting of the MLs which seem to be based on high percentile values of background concentrations in Europe, even for PFAS, as described in Section 2.2.4.

Another option to solve the issue of impractically low EQSs would be to change the methodology for deriving them so that all the EQSs were to be based on ecological risks, which currently holds true for most of the contaminants covered by the EQS Directive anyway. That could make sense, especially for chemicals whose maximum concentrations in drinking water or food are already regulated by relevant legislation targeted at health protection (e.g., the DWD and Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006), such as PFAS. The current situation where the maximum permissible concentrations of PFAS for both drinking water and foodstuffs in their legitimate juridical contexts of safeguarding human health are significantly higher than the corresponding health-risk-based concentrations for surface water, natural fish, and groundwater, seems unjustified both politically and from the practical point of view. This does not mean, however, that the current MLs or DWQs for PFAS should be considered as signifying the most appropriate concentration levels in foodstuffs or drinking water. For example, as proposed for the EQSs above, the consideration of national or regional background concentrations could also be systematically embedded in the application of the MLs. Indeed, the current MLs for PFAS are substantially higher than the representative concentrations in food at most regions and hence cause an unnecessary risk to public health. Lowering the current DWQs, on the other hand, could be justified from both the toxicologic and socio-economic perspective, considering the concentrations levels in European freshwater sources as well as the technical and economic feasibility of treating PFAS-contaminated water at operating water supply facilities (e.g., Ross et al., 2018, Wanninayake, 2021).

Furthermore, recent risk-benefit analyses (RBA) from Finland and Norway demonstrated that the benefits of eating fish generally outweigh

its associated health risks at PFAS concentrations typical for those countries (Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment, 2022, *Opasnet Suomi*, 2021). In the Finnish RBA, based on estimated disability-adjusted life years (DALY) for variable age groups and the national fish monitoring data on PFAS, the same conclusion also applied to the consumption of fish with locally higher PFAS concentrations (mean measured \sum PFAS4 = 7.1 $\mu\text{g}_{\text{ww}}/\text{kg}$), which exceeded the proposed EQS biota nearly 100-fold (*Opasnet Suomi*, 2021). Appropriate RBAs could therefore justify the setting of health-based thresholds for PFAS in fish at substantially higher levels than the proposed EQS biota. However, acknowledging the uncertainties involved in such RBAs and the current toxicity data on PFAS, establishing national, regional, or local dietary recommendations on fish consumption would be a reasonable measure for protecting public health from potentially adverse health effects due to the excess intake of locally caught fish. Such dietary advice could be seen as an expedient tool to supplement any regulatory threshold issued for PFAS in foodstuffs when the feasibility of a threshold due to background concentrations requires to be notably higher than the risk-based level, including the current MLs. So far, dietary recommendations for fish consumption due to PFAS have been issued locally in some jurisdictions both in Europe and elsewhere (*Barbo et al.*, 2023). Moreover, Finland and Sweden have been granted temporary approval to exceed the current MLs for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in certain fish species of the Baltic region, based on their capacity to ensure that consumers are fully informed of the relevant dietary advice regarding such fish, also acknowledging the potential negative health impacts associated with the exclusion of those fish from the diet in that region (*EU*, 2006b).

4. Conclusions

Our study showed that the foundation of the current and proposed European regulatory thresholds for PFAS varies substantially. Consequently, their associated level of health protection differs by several orders of magnitude even in similar regulatory contexts (e.g., ensuring the safety of foodstuffs). This is prone to confusing operators, regulators, and other stakeholders forced to apply the thresholds or to interpret environmental data on PFAS. Such differences can also compromise the consistency of regulatory decisions and risk assessment procedures, and the achievement of their associated policy objectives (e.g., the ‘one-substance one-assessment’ approach). Extreme variation in the thresholds also puts different industries and other parties in unequal positions, potentially inducing considerable economic consequences to those entities that need to comply with the most stringent EQSs, or causing unwarranted health risks to those consumers whose food and drinking water sources contain PFAS in concentrations reaching the DWQSs or the highest MLs. Moreover, the demonstrated inconsistencies and variation between the different thresholds may give rise to questioning the appropriate level of health protection from exposure to PFAS, given that the thresholds specifically intended to safeguard human health in their legitimate juridical contexts (i.e., the MLs and DWQSs) are currently by far the highest regulatory benchmarks.

Understanding the fundamentals and the objectives of a regulatory threshold for any chemical is a prerequisite for promoting its appropriate use and the sustainability of consequent management practices. This necessitates open communication and implicit transparency concerning the rationale behind the threshold including its scientific basis and potential other justifications. The current DWQSs and MLs for PFAS fail to meet such demands as their foundation is neither transparently defined nor publicly available. On the other hand, the fact that the DWQSs and MLs considerably exceed the corresponding risk-based values, i.e., the proposed EQSs, illustrates the inseparable connection and balancing between risk assessment and risk management in regulatory decision-making, including the drafting of legislation. However, adopting the precautionary principle in the face of uncertainty should not underline excess caution, as in the case of the draft EQS biota, and,

on the contrary, feasibility should not be the only determining factor if that is likely to cause unacceptable risks, as might be the case with the DWQSs or the highest MLs. Consequently, a regulatory threshold that cannot be complied with or that mostly ignores the risks – in this case due to the widespread occurrence of PFAS – is effectively useless and likely to complicate rather than mitigate reasonable risk-based decision-making. Allowing flexibility to consider case-specific factors, such as national, regional, or local background concentrations, in the application of the thresholds, and country or region-specific food consumption rates or risk–benefit analyses in their derivation, could partly solve this problem.

Some of the approaches applied in connection with the studied thresholds, such as the RPFs in the case of the draft EQSs, show promising means to regulate PFAS mixtures in a scientifically expedient manner. However, a more thorough understanding of the mechanisms of PFAS toxicity and causal linkages between human exposure to PFAS and consequent health effects at environmentally relevant levels is necessary to properly justify the current grouping approaches and their usability for the determination of regulatory thresholds. Additional data is also needed on several until now less studied substances in the PFAS universe, including the current and future substitutes for restricted PFAS or their precursors. Moreover, the uncertainties regarding the recent epidemiological data on PFAS and the validity of using vaccine response as the critical endpoint for deriving health-based reference values need to be resolved. This also necessitates new research and innovation on the methodological front of regulatory risk assessment.

Based on our findings, we call for an open dialogue on both the scientific and policy aspects of the current and proposed PFAS thresholds to promote rational regulatory development and sustainable management practices on these chemicals. The problems and inconsistencies associated with the thresholds addressed in our study are also likely to emerge with other ubiquitous and bioaccumulative contaminants and should therefore be acknowledged beyond the context of the EU regulation of PFAS.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jussi Reinikainen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elodie Bouhoule:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Jaana Sorvari:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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References

- Abraham, K., Mielke, H., Fromme, H., Völkel, W., Menzel, J., Peiser, M., Zepp, F., Willich, S., Weikert, C., 2019. Internal exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and biological markers in 101 healthy 1-year-old children: associations between levels of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and vaccine response. *Arch. Toxicol.* 94, 2131–2147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-020-02715-4>.
- Ahrens, L., 2011. Polyfluoroalkyl compounds in the aquatic environment: a review of their occurrence and fate. *J. Environ. Monit.* 13 (1), 20–31. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c0em00373e>.
- Andersson, E.M., Scott, K., Xu, Y.Y., Li, Y., Olsson, D.S., Fletcher, T., Jakobsson, K., 2019. High exposure to perfluorinated compounds in drinking water and thyroid disease. A cohort study from Ronneby, Sweden. *Environ. Res.* 176, 108540 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108540>.
- Ankley, G.T., Cureton, P., Hoke, R.A., Houde, M., Kumar, A., Kurias, J., Lanno, R., McCarthy, C., Newsted, J., Salice, C.J., Sample, B.E., Sepúlveda, M.S., Steevens, J., Valsecchi, S., 2021. Assessing the ecological risks of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances: Current state-of-the-science and a proposed path forward. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40 (3), 564–605. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4869>.
- Armstrong, L., Johnson, E., 2018. Water intake, water balance, and the elusive daily water requirement. *Nutrients* 10 (12), 1928. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu10121928>.
- Barbo, N., Stoiber, T., Naidenko, O., Andrews, D., 2023. Locally caught freshwater fish across the United States are likely a significant source of exposure to PFOS and other perfluorinated compounds. *Environ. Res.* 220, 115165 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.115165>.
- Bernardini, I., Matozzo, V., Valsecchi, S., Peruzza, L., Rovere, G., Polesello, S., Iori, S., Marin, M., Fabrello, J., Ciscato, M., Masiero, L., Bonato, M., Santovito, G., Boffo, L., Bargelloni, L., Milan, M., Patarnello, T., 2021. The new PFAS C6O4 and its effects on marine invertebrates: First evidence of transcriptional and microbiota changes in the Manila clam *Ruditapes philippinarum*. *Environ. Int.* 152, 106484 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106484>.
- Bil, W., Zeilmaker, M., Fragki, S., Lijzen, J., Verbruggen, E., Bokkers, B., 2021. Risk assessment of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance mixtures: A relative potency factor approach. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40 (3), 859–870. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4835>.
- Bosgra, S., van der Voet, H., Boon, P., Slob, W., 2009. An integrated probabilistic framework for cumulative risk assessment of common mechanism chemicals in food: An example with organophosphorus pesticides. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharm.* 54 (2), 124–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2009.03.004>.
- Brunn, H., Arnold, G., Körner, W., Rippen, G., Steinhäuser, K., Valentin, I., 2023. PFAS: Forever chemicals — persistent, bioaccumulative and mobile. Reviewing the status and the need for their phase out and remediation of contaminated sites. *Environ. Sci. Environ.* 35 (20), 1–50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-023-00721-8>.
- Brusseau, M.L., Hunter Anderson, R., Guo, B., 2020. PFAS concentrations in soils: Background levels versus contaminated sites. *Sci. Total Environ.* 740, 140017 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140017>.
- Buck, R., Franklin, J., Berger, U., Conder, J., Cousins, I., de Voogt, P., Jensen, A., Kannan, K., Mabury, S., van Leeuwen, S., 2011. Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in the environment: Terminology, classification, and origins. *Integr. Environ. Assess. Manag.* 7 (4), 513–541. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.258>.
- Burgoon, D., Clewell, H., Cox, T., Dekant, W., Dell, L., Deyo, J., Dourson, M., Gadagbui, B., Goodrum, P., Green, L., Vijayavel, K., Kline, T., House-Knight, T., Luster, M., Manning, T., Nathanael, P., Pagone, F., Richardson, K., Severo-Peixe, T., Sharma, A., Wright, J., 2023. Range of the perfluoroctanoate (PFOA) safe dose for human health: An international collaboration. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharm.* 145, 105502 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2023.105502>.
- C8 Science Panel. 2012. Probable Link Evaluation of Infectious Disease, 30 July 2012. <http://www.c8sciencepanel.org/> [accessed 15 August 2023].
- Carvalho R, Marinov D, Loos R, Napierska D, Chirico N, Lettieri T. 2016. Monitoring-based Exercise: Second Review of the Priority Substances List under the Water Framework Directive. <https://circabc.europa.eu/>.
- Chang, E., Adamic, H.O., Boffettad, P., Wedner, J., Mandela, J., 2016. A critical review of perfluorooctanoate and perfluorooctanesulfonate exposure and immunological health conditions in humans. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* 46 (4), 279–331. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10408444.2015.112257>.
- Chohan, A., Petaway, H., Rivera-Diaz, V., Day, A., Colaianni, O., Keramati, M., 2020. Per and polyfluoroalkyl substances scientific literature review: water exposure, impact on human health, and implications for regulatory reform. *Rev. Environ. Health* 36 (2), 235–259. <https://doi.org/10.1515/revh-2020-0049>.
- M Company. 2000. Re: Phase-Out Plan for POSF-based Products. USEPA Administrative Record AR226-0600. <http://www.regulations.gov> as document EPA-HQ-OPPT-2002-0051-0006.
- Cousins, I., DeWitt, J., Glüge, J., Goldenman, G., Herzke, D., Lohmann, R., Miller, M., Ng, C., Scheringer, M., Vierke, L., Wang, Z., 2020. Strategies for grouping per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) to protect human and environmental health. *Environ. Sci. Processes Impacts* 22, 1444. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EM00147C>.
- Deepika, D., Rovira, J., Sabuz, O., Balaguer, J., Schuhmacher, M., Domingo, J., Kumar, V., 2022. Framework for risk assessment of PFAS utilizing experimental studies and in-silico models. *Environ. Res.* 208, 112722 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.112722>.
- EC (European Commission). 2018. Facts and figures on the common fisheries policy. Basic statistical data, 2018 edition, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/294952>.
- EC (European Commission). 2019. Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Findings of the Fitness Check of the most relevant chemicals legislation (excluding REACH) and identified challenges, gaps and weaknesses. COM/2019/264 final, COM/2019/264 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2019:264:FIN>.
- EC (European Commission). 2020a. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment. Brussels, COM/2020/667 final, Document 52020DC0667. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:667:FIN>.
- EC (European Commission). 2020b. Data governance and data policies at the European Commission. https://commission.europa.eu/publications/data-governance-and-data-policies-european-commission_en#details [accessed 30 August 2023].
- EC (European Commission). 2021. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'. COM/2021/400 final, Document 52021DC0400. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0400>.
- EC (European Commission). 2022. ANNEXES to the Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2000/60/EC establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy, Directive 2006/118/EC on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration and Directive 2008/105/EC on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy. COM (2022) 540 final. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/p roposal-amending-water-directives_en.
- ECHA (European Chemicals Agency). 2023. Registry of restriction intentions until outcome. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). <https://echa.europa.eu/registry-of-restriction-intentions/-/dislist/details/0b20236e18663449b> [accessed 20 September 2023].
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2008. Opinion of the Scientific Panel on Contaminants in the Food chain on Perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and their salts. *EFSA Journal*, 6 (7): 653, 131 pp. Doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2008.653.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2018. Scientific Opinion on the risk to human health related to the presence of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and perfluorooctanoic acid in food. *EFSA Journal*, 16 (12): 5194, 284 pp. Doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5194.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2020. Scientific Opinion on the risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. *EFSA Journal*, 18 (9): 6223, 391pp. Doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). 2022. Food consumption data. The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/> [last update 15 December 2022; accessed 20 August 2023].
- Eljarrat E, Barceló D. How do measured PBDE and HCB levels in river fish compare to the European Environmental Quality Standards? *Environmental Research*, 160: 203–211. Doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2017.09.011.
- EU (European Union). 1998. Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption. *Official Journal of the European Union* L 435:1–62.
- EU (European Union). 2006b. Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs. *Official Journal of the European Union* L 364:5–24.
- EU (European Union). 2008. Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. *Official Journal of the European Union* L348:84–97.
- EU (European Union). 2013. Directive 2013/39/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 August 2013 amending Directives 2000/60/EC and 2008/105/EC as regards priority substances in the field of water policy. *Official Journal of the European Union* L226:1–17.
- EU (European Union). 2020. Directive (EU) 2020/2184 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption (recast). *Official Journal of the European Union* L 435/1.
- EU (European Union). 2022. Regulation (EU) 2022/2388 of 7 December 2022 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels of perfluoroalkyl substances in certain foodstuffs. *Official Journal of the European Union* L 316:38–41.
- EUMOFA (European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products), 2021. The EU fish market – 2021 edition. European Commission, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/563899>.
- Fenton, S., Ducatman, A., Boobis, A., DeWitt, J., Lau, C., Ng, C., Smith, J., Roberts, S., 2021. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance toxicity and human health review: Current state of knowledge and strategies for informing future research. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40 (3), 606–630. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4890>.
- Finnish Environment Institute. 2023. Kerty: Finnish database for contaminants in biota and other solid materials (in Finnish; requires registration). <https://ckan.ymparisto.fi/en/dataset/kertymarekisteri-kerty> [accessed 10 June 2023].

- Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare. 2023. Fineli. Food Composition Database in Finland. <https://fineli.fi/fineli/en/index> [accessed 20 September 2023].
- Frisbee, S., Brooks, A., Maher, A., Flensburg, P., Arnold, S., Fletcher, T., Steenland, K., Shankar, A., Knox, S., Pollard, C., Halverson, J., Vieira, V., Jin, C., Leyden, K., Ducatman, A., 2009. The C8 health project: design, methods, and participants. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 117 (12), 1873–1882. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0800379>.
- Fürst P, Milana M, Pfaff K, Tlustos C, Vlemineckx C, Arcella D, Barthélémy E, Colombo P, Goumperis T, Roldán Torres R, Pasinato L, Alfonso A. 2019. Scientific technical assistance to RASFF on chemical contaminants: Risk evaluation of chemical contaminants in food in the context of RASFF notifications. EFSA supporting publication 2019: EN-1625. Doi: 10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1625.
- Ghisi, R., Vamerla, T., Manzetti, S., 2019. Accumulation of perfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) in agricultural plants: A review. *Environ. Res.* 169, 326–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2018.10.023>.
- Glüge, J., Scheringer, M., Cousins, I., DeWitt, J., Goldenman, G., Herzke, D., Lohmann, R., Ng, C., Trier, X., Wang, Z., 2020. An overview of the uses of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). *Environ. Sci. Processes Impacts* 22, 2345. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0em00291g>.
- Goodrum, P., Anderson, J., Luz, A., Ansell, G., 2021. Application of a framework for grouping and mixtures toxicity assessment of PFAS: A closer examination of dose-additivity approaches. *Toxicol. Sci.* 179 (2), 262–278. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfaa123>.
- Haug, L., Thomsen, C., Becher, G., 2009. Time trends and the influence of age and gender on serum concentrations of perfluorinated compounds in archived human samples. *Environ. Sci. Tech.* 43 (6), 2131–2136. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es802827u>.
- ITRC (Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council). 2023. PFAS Technical and Regulatory Guidance Document and Fact Sheets PFAS-1. Washington, D.C.: Interstate Technology & Regulatory Council, PFAS Team. <https://pfas-1.itrcweb.org/> [accessed 7 August 2023].
- Jian, J., Guo, Y., Zeng, L., Liang-ying, L., Lu, X., Wang, F., Zeng, E., 2017. Global distribution of perfluorochemicals (PFCs) in potential human exposure source – A review. *Environ. Int.* 108, 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2017.07.024>.
- Joeris, H., Menger, F., 2023. The complex 'PFAS world' - How recent discoveries and novel screening tools reinforce existing concerns. *Curr. Opin. Green Sustain. Chem.* 40, 100775 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2023.100775>.
- JRC (Joint Research Center). 2022. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). PFAS Final EQS Dossier after SCHEER final opinion. <https://circabc.europa.eu> [accessed 8 August 2023].
- Kirk M, Smurthwaite K, Bräunig J, Trevenar S, D'Este C, Lucas R, Lal A, Korda R, Clements A, Mueller J, Armstrong B. 2018. The PFAS Health Study: Systematic Literature Review. Canberra: The Australian National University.
- Koponen, J., Airaksinen, R., Hallikainen, A., Vuorinen, P., Mannio, J., Kiviranta, H., 2015. Perfluoroalkyl acids in various edible Baltic, freshwater, and farmed fish in Finland. *Chemosphere* 129, 186–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.08.077>.
- Kurwadkar, S., Dane, J., Kanel, S., Nadagouda, M., Cawdrey, R., Ambade, B., Struckhoff, G., Richard, W.R., 2022. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in water and wastewater: A critical review of their global occurrence and distribution. *Sci. Total Environ.* 809 (25), 151003 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151003>.
- Liu, Y., Pereira, A.S., Beeson, S., Vestergren, R., Berger, U., Olsen, G., Glynn, A., Martin, J., 2015. Temporal trends of perfluorooctanesulfonate isomer and enantiomer patterns in archived Swedish and American serum samples. *Environ. Int.* 75, 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2014.11.014>.
- Looker, C., Luster, M., Calafat, A., Johnson, V., Burleson, G., Burleson, F., Fletcher, T., 2014. Influenza vaccine response in adults exposed to perfluorooctanoate and perfluorooctanesulfonate. *Toxicol. Sci.* 138 (1), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kft269>.
- Manea, S., Salmaso, L., Lorenzoni, G., Mazzucato, M., Russo, F., Mantoan, D., Martuzzi, M., Fletcher, T., Facchin, P., 2020. Exposure to PFAS and small for gestational age new-borns: A birth records study in Veneto Region (Italy). *Environ. Res.* 184, 109282 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109282>.
- Natural Resources Institute Finland. 2023. Fish consumption. Statistics database. <http://statdb.luke.fi/PxWeb/pweb/en/LUKE/> [accessed 7 August 2023].
- Noorlander C W, van Leeuwen S P J, te Biesebeek J D, Mengelers M J B, Zeilmaker M J. 2011. Levels of perfluorinated compounds in food and dietary intake of PFOS and PFOA in the Netherlands. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2011, 59 (13): 7496–505 Doi: 10.1021/jf104943p.
- Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment. 2022. Benefit and risk assessment of fish in the Norwegian diet. Scientific Opinion of the Scientific Steering Committee of the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment. VKM Report 2022:17, ISBN: 978-82-8259-392-2, ISSN: 2535-4019.
- Opasnet Suomi. 2021. PFAS-yhdisteiden tautitaakka, 2021 October 14 (in Finnish). http://fi.opasnet.org/fi-opwiki/index.php?title=PFAS-yhdisteiden_tautitaakka&oldid=36878 [accessed 22 August 2023].
- Petit, J.C.J., Peeters, M., Remy, S., 2021. Sustainable health-based soil standards for arsenic using epidemiological data and toxicokinetic/probabilistic modelling. *Environ. Geochem. Health* 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-021-01143-2>.
- Prevedouros, K., Cousins, I.T., Buck, R.C., Korzeniowski, S.H., 2006. Sources, fate and transport of perfluorocarboxylates. *Environ. Sci. Tech.* 40, 32–44. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0512475>.
- Reinikainen, J., Sorvari, J., 2016. Promoting justified risk-based decisions in contaminated land management. *Sci. Total Environ.* 563–564, 783–795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.074>.
- Reinikainen, J., Perkola, N., Äystö, L., Sorvari, J., 2022. The occurrence, distribution, and risks of PFAS at AFFF-impacted sites in Finland. *Sci. Total Environ.* 829, 154237 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154237>.
- Rietjens, I., Schriks M, Houtman C, Dingemans, M, van Wezel A. 2022. Letter to the editor on Bil et al. 2021 "Risk assessment of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance mixtures: A relative potency factor approach". *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 41 (1): 7–12. Doi: 10.1002/etc.5232.
- Ross, I., McDonough, J., Miles, J., Storch, P., Thelakkat Kochunaryanan, P., Kalve, E., Hurst, J., Dasgupta, S., Burdick, J., 2018. A review of emerging technologies for remediation of PFASs. *Remediation* 28, 101–126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rem.21553>.
- Ruffe B, Archer C, Vosnakis K, Butler J,3 Davis C,3 Goldsworthy B, Parkman R, Key T. 2023. US and international per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances surface water quality criteria: A review of the status, challenges, and implications for use in chemical management and risk assessment. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 2023: 1–23. Doi: 10.1002/ieam.4776.
- Ruffe, B., Vedagiri, U., Bogdan, D., Maier, M., Schwach, C., Murphy-Hagan, C., 2020. Perfluoroalkyl substances in U.S. market basket fish and shellfish. *Environ. Res.* 190, 109932 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109932>.
- SCHEER (Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks). 2022. Final Opinion on Draft Environmental Quality Standards for Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive - PFAS, 18 August 2022.
- Schröter-Kermani, C., Müller, J., Jüriling, H., Conrada, A., Schulte, C., 2013. Retrospective monitoring of perfluorocarboxylates and perfluorosulfonates in human plasma archived by the German environmental specimen Bank. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 216 (6), 633–640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2012.08.004>.
- Smalling, K., Romanok, K., Bradley, P., Morriss, M., Gray, J., Kanagy, L., Gordon, S., Williams, B., Breitmeyer, S., Jones, D., DeCicco, L., Eagles-Smith, C., Wagner, T., 2023. Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in United States tapwater: Comparison of underserved private-well and public-supply exposures and associated health implications. *Environ. Int.* 178, 108033 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108033>.
- Smit C, Verbruggen E. 2022. Risicogrenzen voor PFAS in oppervlaktewater. Doorvertaling van de gezondheidskundige grenswaarde van EFSA naar concentraties in water. Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM), RIVM-briefrapport 2022-0074. Doi: 10.21945/rivm-2022-0074.
- Steenland, K., Fletcher, T., Stein, C., Bartell, S., Darrow, L., Lopez-Espinosa, M.J., Ryan, B., Savitz, D., 2020. Review: Evolution of evidence on PFOA and health following the assessments of the C8 science panel. *Environ. Int.* 145, 106125 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106125>.
- US EPA (US Environmental Protection Agency). 2021. Comptox Dashboard. <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/chemical-lists/pfasmaster> [last update 10 August 2021; accessed 4 August 2023].
- US EPA (US Environmental Protection Agency). 2023. Biden-Harris Administration Proposes First-Ever National Standard to Protect Communities from PFAS in Drinking Water. <https://www.epa.gov/newsreleases/biden-harris-administration-proposes-first-ever-national-standard-protect-communities> [last update 14 March 2023; accessed 26 December 2023].
- van den Berg, M., Birnbaum, L., Denison, M., De Vito, M., Farland, W., Feeley, M., Fiedler, H., Hakansson, H., Hanberg, A., Haws, L., Rose, M., Safe, S., Schrenk, D., Tohyama, C., Tritscher, A., Tuomisto, J., Tysklind, M., Walker, N., Peterson, R., 2006. The 2005 World Health Organization re-evaluation of human and mammalian toxic equivalency factors for dioxins and dioxin-like compounds. *Toxicol. Sci.* 93 (2), 223–241. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfl055>.
- van den Berg, M., Birnbaum, L., Denison, M., Birnbaum, L.S., De Vito, M., Fiedler, H., Falandys, J., Rose, M., Schrenk, D., Safe, S., Tohyama, C., Tritscher, A., Tysklind, M., Peterson, R., 2013. Polybrominated dibenzo-p-dioxins, dibenzofurans, and biphenyls: Inclusion in the toxicity equivalency factor concept for dioxin-like compounds. *Toxicol. Sci.* 133 (2), 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kft070>.
- van Dijk, J., Gustavsson, M., Dekker, S., van Wezel, A., 2021. Towards 'one substance – one assessment': An analysis of EU chemical registration and aquatic risk assessment frameworks. *J. Environ. Manage.* 280, 111692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111692>.
- Verstergren R, Cousins I. 2013. Human dietary exposure to per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFASs). In: *Persistent Organic Pollutants and Toxic Metals in Foods*. Elsevier, pp. 279-307. Doi: 10.1533/9780857098917.2.279.
- Wang, Z., Cousins, I., Scheringer, M., Hungerbühler, K., 2013. Fluorinated alternatives to long-chain perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids (PFCAs), perfluoroalkane sulfonic acids (PFASs) and their potential precursors. *Environ. Int.* 60, 242–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2013.08.021>.
- Wanninayake, D., 2021. Comparison of currently available PFAS remediation technologies in water: A review. *J. Environ. Manage.* 283, 111977 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.111977>.
- Washington, J., Rankin, K., Libelo, L., Lynch, D., Cyterski, M., 2019. Determining global background soil PFAS loads and the fluorotelomer-based polymer degradation rates that can account for these loads. *Sci. Total Environ.* 651, 2444–2449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.071>.
- WHO (World Health Organization), 2022. Guidelines for drinking-water quality: fourth edition incorporating the first and second addenda. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
- Young, W., Wiggins, S., Limm, W., Fisher, C., DeJager, L., Genuald, S., 2022. Analysis of per- and poly(fluoroalkyl) substances (PFASs) in highly consumed seafood products

- from U.S. Markets. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 70 (42), 13545–13553. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.2c04673>.
- Zafeiraki, E., Gebbink, W., Hoogenboom, R., Kotterman, M., Kwadijk, C., Dassenakis, E., van Leeuwen, S., 2019. Occurrence of perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in a large number of wild and farmed aquatic animals collected in the Netherlands. *Chemosphere* 232, 415–423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.05.200>.
- Zeilmaker M, Fragki S, Verbruggen E, Bokkers B, Lijzen J. 2018. Mixture exposure to PFAS: A Relative Potency Factor approach. RIVM Report 2018-0070. Doi: 10.21945/RIVM-2018-0070.

Further reading

- EU (European Union). 2006a. Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration. *Official Journal of the European Union* L372:19–31.